

Scenario risk assessment of landslides – Asenovgrad mountain road

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Abstract. As a part of the Reimbursable Advisory Services on Accelerating Resilience to Disaster Risks, the World Bank has supported the Ministry of Interior, General Directorate for Fire Safety and Civil Protection in developing a proposal for the National Disaster Risk Profile of Bulgaria. The article presents initial data, methodologies, and results used in the landslide risk assessment in Bulgaria in connection with the Fourth Technical Annex used in the landslide risk assessment of Bulgaria. A scenario-based methodology is developed and implemented on a national level. Risk assessment results are presented in five main categories: physical safety, security of physical assets and critical infrastructure, economic security, social well-being, and natural environment security.

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INTRODUCTION

The present paper presents a landslide risk assessment and scientific research done under the “Landslide Risk in Bulgaria. Technical Annex 4” under the World Bank’s project “Reimbursable Advisory Services on Accelerating Resilience to Disaster Risks” (P170629); Component 3: National Disaster Risk Profile. The main methodology is based on International Standard: International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 31010:2019 Risk management – Risk assessment techniques, and Joint Research Centre – European Commission (JRC-EC) recommendation.

On the basis of available and accessible information concerning registered landslides in Bulgaria, some characteristic sections have been selected of the widely manifested landslide phenomena in cer-

tain landslide regions (Berov *et al.*, 2002; Bruchev *et al.*, 2007; Ivanov *et al.*, 2017a, 2022; Bruchev, 2018). According to the requirement of the World Bank and the International Electrotechnical Commission, three possible scenarios with different probabilities of occurrence and possible consequences were selected for risk assessment. Here is presented one of them.

METHODOLOGY

According to the worldwide established terminology, landslides are a type of movement of earth masses down a slope under the direct influence of gravity (*e.g.*, USGS, 2021). For the purposes of this paper, the term landslide shall refer to all types of gravitational mass movements described in Varnes

(1978) classification as rotational landslides, translational landslides, lateral spreads, earthflows, as well as complex landslides.

All these types of slope movements are included in the National Program for Prevention and Limitation of Landslides on the Territory of the Republic of Bulgaria (Dobrev *et al.*, 2015) and Geological Risk Mapping (Ivanov *et al.*, 2017b) assigned by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (MRDPW).

This study also considered landslide risk assessment practices in Greece (NRA-GR, 2019) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (https://europa.ba/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/HRA_Final_web.pdf), the European Union Joint Research Center risk assessment guidelines, the disaster risk management guidelines of the Australian Society of Geomechanics (https://landsliderisk.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/ags_2007c2.pdf) as well as the approach for risk assessment of natural phenomena applied in the National Risk Profile of the Netherlands (<https://www.clingendael.org/publication/national-risk-profile-2016>).

Landslide risk assessment goes through three stages: hazard assessment, vulnerability assessment and exposure assessment. It is based on the JRC-EC recommendation (Poljanšek, 2019):

$$R = H \times V \times E,$$

where risk (R) is a function of hazard (H), vulnerability (V), and exposure (E). For detailed definitions of these terms see Table 1.

The risk is assessed using quantitative (deterministic and probabilistic) methods and is based on the scenarios of hypothetical disaster events in the country presented in the next chapter.

Hazard

Landslide hazard is rated on a scale from 0 to 1 (or 0% to 100%), where 0 represents the absence of landslide processes, while 1 means a landslide of a very high intensity (and, accordingly, a very high degree of hazard).

Hazard can be expressed by the formula:

$$H = M \times P,$$

where H = hazard; M = magnitude of the landslide; P = probability.

A landslide risk assessment system was proposed Fell (1994), including the following prerequisites, assumptions, and components:

1. Classification of the manifested or potential landslide is according to Varnes (1978);
2. A landslide is characterized by magnitude (M) depending on its volume in m^3 (Table 2);
3. Classification of landslide hazard according to their magnitude and probability of occurrence (Table 3).

This approach to landslides is also adopted in the Methodology for Geological Risk Assessment in Bulgaria (Dobrev *et al.*, 2014) and is applied in the subsequent Geological Risk Mapping (Ivanov *et al.*, 2017b).

In this case, the magnitude will be estimated by the formula:

$$M = \alpha \times G \times k.$$

In the above formula α are the threat levels according to slope inclination and G – threat levels according to the geological structure as described by Ivanov *et al.* (2017a). The coefficient k used in the formula aims to equate the result obtained with

Table 1
Definitions of key terms

Term	Definition
Risk	Potential disaster losses that may occur to a community, including life, health status, livelihoods, assets and services, in a certain time period. Risk is defined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure and vulnerability.
Hazard	A dangerous phenomenon, substance, human activity or condition that may cause loss of life, injury or other health consequences, property damage, loss of livelihood and services, social and economic disruptions or environmental damage.
Exposure	People, property, systems or other elements in hazard-prone areas subject to potential losses.
Vulnerability	The characteristics and state of a community, system or asset that make them susceptible to the harmful factors of a given hazard.

Table 2
Classification of landslides by magnitude (M). Source: Fell (1994) and Methodology for geological risk assessment in Bulgaria (Dobrev et al., 2014).

M	Description	Volume (m ³)	
7	Extremely large	>5 000 000	
6	Very large	>1 000 000	<5 000 000
5	Moderately large	>250 000	<1 000 000
4	Moderate	> 50 000	<250 000
3	Small	> 5 000	<50 000
2	Very small	>500	<5 000
1	Tiny	<500	

Table 3
Landslide hazard classification ($H = M \times P$). Source: Fell (1994) and Methodology for geological risk assessment in Bulgaria (Dobrev et al., 2014)

H	Description
≥ 30	Extremely high
$\geq 20 - < 30$	Very high
$\geq 10 - < 20$	High
$\geq 7 - < 10$	Medium
$\geq 3 - < 7$	Low
≥ 2	Very low

the final values of magnitude in Table 2. In our case, $k = 0.07$.

Probability

Probability (P) of landslide occurrence is assessed using the following formula (Crovelli, 2000):

$$P = 1 - e^{-T/RI},$$

where RI is the recurrence interval, T is the number of years in the interval under consideration, i.e., 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, etc. years.

$$RI = \frac{n + 1}{m},$$

where n is the number of years of observation; m is the number of registered cases.

Unfortunately, in most cases, we handle incomplete historical data. In this case, RI is calculated by the formula:

$$RI = \frac{t}{N},$$

where t is the time interval of the landslide, N is the number of registered landslides on the slope.

Thus, the proposed approach fully satisfies the requirement to indicate the frequency of activation; however, there is one drawback: we have incomplete (at some sites) or limited data regarding frequency of activation. Such data are available for the period since the 1970s. The applied working principle is to calculate the probability of activation not of a specific landslide, but of an entire slope (or of a small area with similar conditions in terms of geology, landscape and groundwater). Where sufficient data are not available for a section, expert judgement is applied by analogy of sections with similar conditions.

Uncertainty/confidence

Uncertainty (confidence) is a parameter that characterizes security of presented measurement data. This parameter can be added (or subtracted) from the result of a measurement that claims to be the true value. It is usually denoted by the letter δ . In the most general case of monitoring data analysis, laboratory analyses, etc., this is the ratio of the error to the measured (known) value. In our case, it reflects the security of the data we use. Uncertainty (confidence) is expressed qualitatively and varies from low confidence (unconvincing evidence or disagreement between experts) to very high confidence (strong evidence and high consensus).

By default, we have high (**H**), medium (**M**), and low (**X**) uncertainty:

- High (**H**) uncertainty: unconvincing evidence (limited sources, extrapolations, contradictory findings, poor documentation and/or unverified methods, etc.), disagreement or lack of opinion among experts;

- Medium (**M**) uncertainty: Suggestive evidence (multiple sources, limited sequence, incomplete models, etc.);

- Low (**X**) uncertainty: Strong to moderate evidence (multiple or some sources, consistent results, good documentation, etc.), high consensus.

In the present analysis, we have assumed conditionally that:

- High (**H**) uncertainty is observed at $\delta < 35\%$;
- Medium (**M**) uncertainty is observed at $35\% \leq \delta < 70\%$;
- Low (**X**) uncertainty is observed at $\delta \geq 70\%$ reliability of the information used.

Input Data

For the purposes of this study, the team has used updated data provided by the MRDPW on landslides in the country, included in the National Register. In selecting suitable sites for development of hypothetical representative scenarios for significant landslides, as well as the frequency of landslide activations, the working team has received valuable information from Geo-Protection companies in

Varna, Pleven and Pernik, and has discussed various possible scenarios with them. For some data, the team has also used its own sources. It should be noted here that the team visited and conducted field research in the three areas selected for the scenarios, gathering and verifying the necessary information on site. The working team received support and data from the regional directorates “Fire safety and civil protection” and mayoralties of settlements where there are manifestations of landslides, as well as from the MRDPW.

Own data are used for the geological basis, based on the geological map of Bulgaria in scale 1:500000, and in addition the new coefficients (hazard levels) have been added to the attribute table according to the geological structure. The geomorphological basis (landscape) is based on a digital elevation model (DEM) – free access data.

SCENARIO: PROBABLE SCENARIO – LANDSLIDE ALONG A MOUNTAIN ROAD

The scenario takes place in a section of the road Asenovgrad–Smolyan (II-86), 1.6 km from Asenovgrad

Fig. 1. Geological map of the area (after Sarov *et al.*, 2008): 1) Quaternary sediments; Asenitsa Lithotectonic Unit: 2) Marbles, medium-grained (As/c); 3) Biotite and amphibole-biotite gneisses and gneiss-schists (As/bg); 4) Biotite schists with or without garnet and garnet-epidote schists (As/sh); 5) Amphibolites (As/a); 6) Biotite metagranite (As/bim).

and 6.5 km from Bachkovo Monastery, second-class road II-86 is one of the busiest in the country, with traffic reaching an average of ~ 20 000 cars per day. In the studied section, it is about 5000 cars per day.

The conditions under which the landslide is activated are the following: mountainous landscape with steep slopes (20–30° and more). The geological base is represented by metamorphic rocks (marbles, gneisses, etc.), as the road section before Asenova Krepost (Asen’s Fortress) crosses a ground fault zone, about 100 m wide, which is traced to about 800 m in depth in the slope (Sarov *et al.*, 2008; Fig. 1).

There is a known landslide activation that occurred in 2009 and formed in the fault area. In 2015,

after a new activation, the main road was interrupted, the secondary road was distorted. Another activation was registered in 2018.

A 33% probability of landslide activation within 5 years is calculated (Table 4).

SCENARIO DESCRIPTION AND RESULTS

The scenario develops in late winter after prolonged precipitation combined with intense snowmelt. The activation takes place at night and comes as a surprise to drivers on the road. Landslide’s movement was going on very fast and 80 m of road II-86 (Asenovgrad–Smolyan) are interrupted, as well as the side road to two isolated villages in the area. Two

Table 4
Input data used to calculate probability in the scenario

Scenario	Period	No. of years	Cases	Return Interval, <i>RI</i> [years]	Probability of occurrence in 5 years, <i>P</i>
2	1970–2019	50	4	12.5	33%

Fig. 2. Location of the landslide.

Fig. 3. General view of the landslide: *a, b*) Collapsed slope on the road Asenovgrad–Smolyan (II-86), 1.6 km from Asenovgrad in the direction of Bachkovo Monastery (picture taken on April 3, 2015); *c, d*) Damaged asphalt on the road Asenovgrad– Asen’s Fortress (picture taken on April 3, 2015).

roads are interrupted: main road, with accumulated material on it; secondary road, interrupted and collapsed on both sides of the landslide. No residential buildings are affected (Figs 2, 3).

Communications between Asenovgrad and a number of settlements have been cut off (Chepelare, Smolyan, and the villages in the area); there is no access to Asen’s Fortress. Access from Asenovgrad to Bachkovo Monastery, Narechen and the mountain resorts is via a long bypass road. There are difficulties in supply of goods, access to workplaces in an area with 7000 inhabitants.

The sudden landslide at night resulted in accidents with minimal casualties and injuries.

Following the cutoff of this important road artery, the local economy is experiencing temporary difficulties. This leads to an insignificant increase in unemployment during the recovery period. The limited access to the two isolated villages takes longer.

About a week is needed to clear the road. Reconstruction of the road to the isolated villages (110

inhabitants) is slower due to the still unattenuated movements. It is necessary to use longer bypass routes. Urgent preventive measures are also required to prevent landslide masses from reaching the Chepelarska River, which may create conditions for its obstruction.

A summary of the impact of the landslide scenario is presented in Table 5.

CONCLUSIONS

The present article presents a methodology for natural disaster risk assessment according to the IEC 31010:2019 Risk management – Risk assessment techniques. It is developed and implemented for the first time for landslide risk assessment in Bulgaria.

For the achievement of maximum credibility results, the uncertainty (confidence) parameter is used and divided into three main levels: low, medium and high uncertainty.

Table 5
Landslide scenario impact summary

Scenario likelihood							Explanation
	Almost certain	Very likely	Likely	Unlikely	Very rare		
Likelihood of scenario occurring in the next 5 years			X			12.5-year return period	
Scenario impact							
National interest	Impact criterion	Impact severity					Explanation of the impact
		Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic	
Physical safety	Fatalities		H				1–2 fatalities due to car accidents
	Injured and chronically ill		H				1–2 injuries due to car accidents
	People requiring temporary accommodations or permanently displaced	X					No people in need of shelter
Security of physical assets and critical infrastructure	Damage to buildings	X					No destroyed buildings
	Damage to cultural heritage	X					No affected monuments of cultural significance
	Damage to CI and disruption to operation of CI			X			Interruption of the main and secondary roads, the only ones accessing two villages
Economic security	Impact on the economy		X				Difficulties in transport between the two towns, requiring use of longer detour routes; difficulties in tourism and mountain resorts
	Impact on key economic sectors			M			Difficulties in transport and tourism; difficulties moving goods in both directions
Social well-being	Disruption of everyday life			M			Difficulties in transport and tourism
	Income loss and unemployment	X					Difficulties in the supply and distribution of goods; temporary difficulties in tourism; local economy continues working
	Disruption to key societal functions			M			Disruption of key public functions for several days
Natural environment security	Destruction of natural assets		X				A small area under the road falls in a Natura 2000 site
	Long-term disruptions to the environment	X					No impact

Note: X = low uncertainty; M = medium uncertainty; H = high uncertainty.

The obtained data show stable relevance with the real events and empirical data analysis.

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